

CO-ORDINATED MERCURY COMPOUNDS WITH ETHYLENE AND PROPYLENEDIAMINES.

BY PANCHANAN NEOGI AND KANAI LAL MONDAL

Two different series of complex mercuric salts with propylenediamines have been described, one series is insoluble and the other soluble in water.

Though some complex mercuric salts with ethylenediamine are known for sometime, no such compounds with propylenediamine have hitherto been prepared. In this paper, two different series of complex mercuric salts with propylenediamine are described. In one of them mercuric salts combine with the free diamine in equimolecular proportions and form mono-compounds, which are insoluble in water. In the other series, one molecule of a mercuric salt enters into combination with one molecule of a salt of the diamine and forms a complex compound, which dissolves very readily in water. It is to be noted that whilst the solubility of ordinary mercuric salts such as mercuric chloride is of a very limited order, the solubility of the complex mercuric salts of the second series, described here, is very great. These very soluble salts of mercury must possess valuable therapeutic effects the nature and extent of which are being studied. Attempts at preparation of complex mercuric salts with propylenediamine resulted, as in the case of ethylenediamine, in their immediate decomposition with precipitation of grey metallic mercury and the corresponding mercuric salts.

The mono-compounds of the first series dissolve in excess of the diamine and give clear solutions, but compounds of definite composition could be isolated from them. Possibly bis-compounds are formed but being very unstable they decompose immediately. Compounds of both the series are more or less stable in air but are easily destroyed by dilute acids and alkalis.

In addition to the complex propylenediamine mercuric salts, several new ethylenediamine compounds of both the series have been described.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Propylenediamine-mercuric Chloride.—Mercuric chloride (1 mol.) dissolved in alcohol was added to propylenediamine (1 mol., 70% solution) when a white precipitate of the complex chloride was formed. The same compound was also obtained from an aqueous solution of mercuric chloride.

It is insoluble in water and melts with decomposition above 250°. {Found : N, 8.0 ; Cl, 20.31 ; Hg, 58.35. [Hg pn] Cl₂ requires N, 8.11 ; Cl, 20.58 ; Hg, 57.97 per cent}.

Propylenediamine-mercuric Bromide.—Mercuric bromide (1 mol.) dissolved in alcohol was added to a molecule of propylenediamine when the complex bromide was precipitated as a white substance. It was washed with water and alcohol and dried in an ordinary desiccator. It melted with decomposition but the melting point was very high. It could not be dissolved in any of the common organic solvents and did not change on keeping. {Found : N, 6.70 ; Br, 37.22 ; Hg, 46.31. [Hg pn] Br₂ requires N, 6.45 ; Br, 36.87 ; Hg, 46.08 per cent}.

Propylenediamine-mercuric Nitrate.—A saturated solution of mercuric nitrate was prepared and propylenediamine was added to the solution till it ceased to give any white precipitate. The precipitate was washed with water and dried. Excess of water produced hydrolysis and prevented the formation of the complex nitrate. {Found : N, 13.82 ; Hg 50.30, [Hg pn]-(NO₃)₂ requires N, 14.07 ; Hg, 50.25 per cent}.

Propylenediamine Hydrochloride Compound of Mercuric Chloride.—To a saturated solution of mercuric chloride, propylenediamine hydrochloride (1 mol.) dissolved in the least quantity of water was added. The complex chloride was precipitated as white substance. If the solutions used are dilute no precipitate is formed and the mixed solutions have got to be evaporated in vacuum to obtain the complex salt. The precipitate was washed with alcohol several times and then twice crystallised from water. The crystals are very soluble in water and decompose readily with dilute acids including acetic acid. {Found : N, 6.56 ; Cl, 33.5 ; Hg, 47.53. [Hg pn·2HCl] Cl₂ requires N, 6.69 ; Cl, 33.97 ; Hg, 47.84 per cent}.

Propylenediamine Hydrobromide Compound of Mercuric Bromide.—Mercuric bromide was dissolved in alcohol and an equimolecular quantity of propylenediamine hydrobromide, dissolved in the least quantity of water, was added to it. No precipitate was formed. On the addition of a mixture of alcohol and ether, however, a white precipitate of the complex bromide was obtained. It was washed with alcohol thoroughly and then crystallised several times from water in which it was very soluble. {Found : N, 4.48 ; Br, 53.42 ; Hg, 33.21. [Hg pn·2HBr] Br₂ requires N, 4.69 ; Br, 53.67. Hg, 33.55.}

Propylenediamine Hydroiodide Compound of Mercuric Iodide.—To a molecule of an alcoholic solution of mercuric iodide, one molecule of an aqueous solution of propylenediamine hydroiodide was added and the mixture allowed to evaporate in vacuum. A yellowish coloured substance

gradually appeared. It became almost white on crystallising from water. The product was impure. It had to be purified by crystallising several times from water. The complex iodide is even more soluble than the corresponding chloride and bromide and decomposes easily on exposure to air or on keeping for a long time. The colour of the substance then becomes yellow. {Found : N, 3'85 ; I, 64'38 ; Hg, 25'70. [Hg pn. 2 HI]₂ requires N, 3'57 ; I, 64'79 ; Hg, 25'51 per cent}.

Propylenediamine Nitrate Compound of Mercuric Nitrate.—To an aqueous solution of mercuric nitrate, an equimolecular proportion of propylenediamine was added. No precipitate was formed. But on the addition of alcohol to the mixture, a precipitate of the complex nitrate gradually appeared. It was perfectly white in colour. {Found : N, 16'39 ; Hg, 37'65. [Hg pn. 2 HNO₃] (NO₃)₂ requires N, 16'03 ; Hg, 38'17 per cent}.

Ethylenediamine-mercuric nitrate was prepared in the same way as the corresponding propylenediamine compound. {Found : N, 14'77 ; Hg, 51'76. [Hg pn] (NO₃)₂ requires N, 14'58 ; Hg, 52'08 per cent}.

Ethylenediamine nitrate compound of mercuric nitrate salt was prepared in the same way as the corresponding propylenediamine compound. {Found : N, 16'71 ; Hg, 39'02. [Hg pn. 2HNO₃]₂ requires N, 16'47 ; Hg, 39'21 per cent}.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
PRESIDENCY COLLEGE,
CALCUTTA.

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